

colour ● Sr_spike ● Caliper Measurement ● NA

C. edule G003

C. edule G511

C. edule G600

C. edule G457

C. edule G472

C. edule G555

M. edulis G177

M. edulis G191

M. edulis G259

O. edulis G271

O. edulis G282

O. edulis G372

